

LOCAL INNOVATION IN INCLUSIVE EDUCATION: AN IMPLEMENTATION STUDY IN 3 DISTRICTS

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ABSTRACT

Every child, including children with special needs, is guaranteed of their right to receive educational service. Said educational service has to be available, and affordable. Regardless of physical, mental, social, economic and geographic obstacles, educational rights should be fulfilled without any discrimination (Regulation of National Education System, Number 2, 2003). Ministry of National Education has stipulated Minister Regulation Number 70, 2009 concerning inclusive education. Several regencies have initiated to realize the policy. How far the policy has been realized? Research team from UNESA University in corporation with SEBELAS MARET University has organized research in three districts, which are Surakarta that has executed three years of implementation, Gresik that has executed two years of implementation, and Batu that has executed one year of implementation. Research result showed significant progress in achievement and actualization of inclusive education in said three districts. Innovation and support from stakeholders, and also utilization of local resources, aid to facilitate its progress. The progress can be presented in qualitative and quantitative indicators.

Preface

Every child, including children with special needs, is guaranteed of their right to receive educational service without any discrimination (Regulation of National Education System, Number 2, 2003). Therefore, said service availability and affordability has to be considered equally important. Physical, mental, social, economic and geographic obstacles should not be any excuse to deprive a child's right to get proper education.

In the last 4 years, the government, specifically Ministry of Education and Culture, has attempted innovation through inclusive education movement, by comprehensive approach using region-based method. In previous years, inclusive education was implemented by school-based method. Until year end of 2014, at least there were 60 regions that have implemented intensive movement on inclusive education, which consist of 12 provinces and 48 regencies.

This movement is performed by optimizing local government's role and potential. For instance, by aiding through local initiatives and funding, forming work groups, training and

mentoring expert staffs, and providing stimulants in terms of social assistance from central government.

In order to understand implementation effectiveness, as well as monitoring, field research is proven essential to observe discrepancy between policy and implementation based on assigned indicators differences. Furthermore, identification of initiatives and innovations being developed on local level is also vital.

Research team from UNESA University and SEBELAS MARET University, together with Special Needs and Services Directorate, and also FATAHA Education and Training Center, cooperated to carry out field research. This paper will describe results obtained from 3 District that have applied the movement for over 3 years (Surakarta District), 2 years (Gresik District), and 1 year (Batu District).

Besides interview, data collection was also completed by FGD (focus group discussion) with corresponding officials. Assembled data, which contain field footnotes too, were further selected so that future focus can be presented, analyzed and derived conclusion from. Research procedures utilize qualitative method to describe written words and observed attitude (Maleong, 2002:3). Phenomenon is described based on inspected phenomenon indicators (Slamet, 2006:7).

Meanwhile, data source is originated from:

1. Working group core committee
2. Headmasters of elementary schools, junior high schools, high schools, and Special School
3. Education District Authority and other corresponding authorities
4. Teachers
5. Documents, such as photos, local regulations, report guides, etc.

Assembled data was further selected to be focused, established into abstract, organized into display, analyzed into gap policy, and obtained conclusion (Sugiono, 2011:47).

Basic Concept

Inclusive education is an educational organization system which provides opportunity for every learner with special need and/or special talent to follow education or learning process in educational environment alongside common learners (Article 1 of Minister of National Education Regulation, No 70, 2009).

The above description is in accordance with “*Bhinneka Tunggal Ika*” spirit, as a symbol of recognition that Indonesia is truly a multicultural, multiethnic, multilingual, multi customs, also multi religions and beliefs that can coexist peacefully. Hence, this spirit should be protected, fostered and developed, among others, through educational process that values multiple differences – education for mixture of citizens that is devoid of discrimination.

Government, families and parents alike are required to offer opportunity as wide as possible to every child to acquire appropriate education.

For that reason, inclusive education is aimed to (1) provide opportunity as wide as possible to every learner in accordance with each personal characteristics and abilities to acquire education which has suitable quality for each person's needs and abilities, (2) realize educational organization that is equal to every learner without discrimination and values diversity.

There are several factors that influence inclusive education (Yusuf, 2011), such as (1) headmaster's management and leadership, (2) teacher's knowledge, perception, competence, and proficiency, (3) cooperation with other parties, (4) obstruction level of children with special needs (5) facilities, infrastructure and financial support, and (6) attitude and acceptance of all school components.

Figure 2.1 - Factors affecting inclusive school accomplishment

Concerning support from both central and local government, local government role is crucial to (1) ensure enactment of national regulation into local regulation, (2) establish working groups, (3) offer training and mentoring, (4) provide support as funding source, (5)

provide socialization to all stakeholders. Meanwhile, central government role is crucial to (1) establish national regulation, (2) encourage local government to implement inclusive education movement, (3) provide guidelines of inclusive education, (4) allocate funding as stimulant to the movement, and (5) present award to individuals with significant contribution.

Local Initiative and Innovation

Surakarta District

Surakarta is one of Central Java districts that once became a center of Surakarta Kingdom. Its area extends to 44.04 km², consists of 5 sub-districts and 51 administrative villages. In 2014, total amount of children with special needs in the district reaches 1,882 individuals. 1,217 are enrolled in special schools, and 399 are enrolled in regular schools.

Through local government's initiative, the inclusive education movement has flourished rapidly.

1. The number of inclusive schools has increased from 13 (in 2012) to 29 schools (in 2014).
2. The number of schools that serve as Resources Center has increased from 1 to 5 schools.
3. Itinerant teachers have also grown from 98 to 126 individuals. They are prepared through specific training.
4. Regulations are prepared by enactment of Mayor's Regulation of Inclusive Education Number 25a, 2014, and Authority Chief's Decree regarding school model and Resources Center. These regulations complement existing local regulations regarding child protection.
5. APBD (Regional Government Budget) allotment for inclusive education is:
2013 = IDR 150 million
2014 = IDR 1.3 billion
2015 = IDR 1.3 billion

The above budget is allocated for Resources Center development, on teachers, headmasters and itinerant teachers training, and as well as accessibility improvement.

6. Autistic center was constructed in Surakarta by funding shared between local government and Ministry of National Education.

By effort described in above, participation index has flourished to 85.8%.

Table 3.1 - Gap analysis of Surakarta district

Number	Measured Aspect	Previous Year	Current Condition	Expected Condition
1	Number of children with special needs	1490	1882	-
2	Number of Special School	17	32	-
3	Number of inclusive school	13	29	-
4	Number of Resources Center	1	5	-
5	Number of itinerant teacher	98	126	-
6	Regulation availability	Available	Available (see above)	-
7	Regional Government Budget availability	-	IDR 930 million	± IDR 1.3 billion
8	Inclusive working group availability	Not available	Available	-
9	Grand design availability	Not available	Available	-
10	Percentage of NER	-	85.8%	-
11	Data center availability	Not available	Available	-

Gresik District

Gresik is one of East Java districts situated next to Surabaya city (which is the capital of East Java province). Its area extends to 1,191.25 km², consists of 18 sub-districts, 26 administrative villages and 356 villages. Most population make their living in service and port industry.

After intensively implementing inclusive education for 2 years, results showed significant progress in participation of children with special needs' education (63.7% Net Enrollment Ratio of children with special needs).

1. The number of inclusive school show considerable increase.
 2012 = 25 schools (pre-launching)
 2013 = 26 schools
 2014 = 42 schools
 2015 = 81 schools
2. The presence of service innovation is proven by development of 1 Resources Center and 7 sub-Resources Center.
3. Itinerant teachers were newly recruited and trained, adding personnel from 15 (in 2012) to 110 individuals (in 2015).
4. Local regulations were newly enacted by issuing:
 1. District's Regulation (Perbub) of inclusive education

2. Decree of inclusive school
3. Decree of itinerant teacher
4. Decree of Resources Center addition
5. Local Government regulation (Perda) of inclusive education
5. 5 years action program was designed meticulously, followed by massive socialization through television, radio, website and newspaper continuously.
6. APBD (Regional Government Budget) allotment for inclusive education is:
 - 2013 = IDR 100 thousand per child monthly
 - 2014 = IDR 850 million
 - 2015 = IDR 1.12 billion

The above budget is allocated for Resources Center development, scholarship for all children with special needs, as well as subsidy for inclusive school and inclusive education training.

Table 3.2 - Gap analysis of Gresik district

Number	Measured Aspect	Previous Year	Current Condition	Expected Condition
1	Number of children with special needs	563	1256	-
2	Number of Special School	-	23	-
3	Number of inclusive school	25	81	81
4	Number of Resources Center	1	8	8
5	Number of itinerant teacher	15	110	110
6	Regulation availability	Available	Available	Available
7	Regional Government Budget availability	IDR 100.000 per student monthly	IDR 850 million	± IDR 1.12 billion
8	Inclusive work group availability	-	Available	Available
9	Grand design availability	Available	Available	Available
10	Percentage of NER	-	63.7%	-
11	Data center availability	-	Available	Available

Batu District

Batu district extends to 197.087 km², consists of 3 sub-districts, 5 administrative villages and 19 villages. What separates Batu from Surakarta and Gresik, is that Batu is famous as mountainous tourist area.

After 1 year of implementing inclusive education, Batu's local government started an initiative to improve educational service for children with special needs by:

1. Enhancing status of special schools by constructing new school
2. Training regular schools to be inclusive schools, from 10 to 23 schools
3. Developing 1 special school and 2 elementary school to be school-based Resources Center
4. Training itinerant teachers from 20 to 35 individuals
5. Enacting regulations through Mayor's Regulation No 24, 2013
6. Allocating APBD of IDR 100 million annually
7. Composing grand design concerning inclusive education socialization for 5 years period

Table 3.3 - Gap analysis of Batu district

Number	Measured Aspect	Previous Year	Current Condition	Expected Condition
1	Number of children with special needs	266	539	-
2	Number of Special School	3	3	3
3	Number of inclusive school	10	23	63
4	Number of Resources Center	1	2	5
5	Number of itinerant teacher	20	35	62
6	Regulation availability	Available	Available (see above)	Available
7	Regional Government Budget availability	-	IDR 75 million	± IDR 200 million
8	Inclusive work group availability	-	Available	Available
9	Grand design availability	Available	Available	Available
10	Percentage of NER	-	60.1%	-
11	Data center availability	-	Available	Available

Conclusion and Recommendation Conclusion

1. Local government role is crucial to establish local initiative and innovation in inclusive education movement by complying guidelines from central government.
2. Inclusive education can be performed by enacting local regulation, forming working groups, offering training and socialization supported by local government funding.
3. Professional assistance is necessary to design action programs and perform them systematically.

4. Since Indonesia government has reformed from centralize to decentralize system, national regulations need to be transformed into local regulations.

Recommendation

1. Impact from inclusive education movement at discussed districts is highly positive to cater educational access for children with special needs. Hence, this movement needs to be constantly evaluated and developed.
2. Funding shared between central and local government is proven to be effective in inclusive education movement. Therefore, such mechanism will be vital in the future. Central government funding can be settled as inclusive education movement's stimulant.
3. Working group has significant function in coordinating the process. Hence, Education Agency needs to assign roles to facilitate inclusive education's subjects in schools.
4. Itinerant teachers must be professionally prepared, as well as be well provided of their rights and incentives.
5. Local regulation has to be benefited as reference, including to authorize planning, programs, and implementation of action programs, and also, to nurture local potential power.
6. Society's active participation must be encouraged to nurture collective awareness of education for children with special needs.
7. Professional expert staffs' mentoring is required throughout planning stage to implementation and evaluation stage. College role is also greatly required.
8. Further study is required to be done in all districts that has implemented inclusive education movement as a part of program evaluation.

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